

Original Research Report

E-Marketing of Clothing Products and Consumers' Satisfaction of Delivery Methods in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The rapid development of information technology led to a cultural shift in means of marketing and commerce. The study determined e-marketing of clothing products and consumers' satisfaction with delivery methods in Epe Local Government Area of Lagos State. Four research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population for the study was 181,715 household members. The sample size for the study was 384. Researcher-developed validated questionnaire was utilized for data collection. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings indicated that the clothing products commonly purchased online included personal clothes such as gowns, jeans, shirts, shoes, handbags, jewelry, and wristwatches. Findings showed that the most common delivery method was the use of courier service. Findings revealed that the customers are satisfied with e-marketing vendors when goods ordered are delivered well packed without dents on products and when goods ordered are delivered on agreed time without delay. Results also showed that the problems customers face in e-marketing of clothing products' delivery method included when products delivered are not the same quality as products ordered and when e-marketing vendors waste time in delivering products ordered. Among recommendations made was that customers can compare varying prices online while engaging in online purchases. Also, the right delivery method should be adopted to ensure customer satisfaction.

Keywords: Clothing, Customer's Satisfaction, Delivery, e-marketing, Products.

1. Introduction

The rapid development of information technology led to a cultural shift in means of marketing and commerce. COVID-19 pandemic also popularized e-commerce which led to the emergence of e-marketing of different products. E-Marketing also known as electronic marketing refers to the marketing conducted over the Internet. Wang and Le (2015) defined e-marketing as the process of marketing a brand (company, product or service) using the internet through computers and mobile devices. E-marketing is an area of marketing that is based on achieving targets and reaching audience through electronic communication technology on the internet.

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Post COVID-19 enabled online shopping experience an explosive growth due to the fact that it represents a more economic and convenient approach to purchasing in comparison to traditional shopping. E-marketing focuses on marketing products, goods and services online. The e-marketing vendor may use direct or indirect marketing features on the internet to connect the products or services to new customers, retain present customers, and build a brand identity. In e-marketing, vendors use strategies and techniques which utilize online activities to reach target customers. E-marketing allows a business to reach its customers in a wide range of ways such as website, email, live chat, blog, forums and statuses. Sarthak (2020) noted that e-commerce has redefined ways consumers make choices while shopping as it is easy and comfortable to shop online and get the products delivered to ones doorstep.

Due to the features of the internet, e-customers can be anywhere in the world. Different from typical marketing methodologies, the internet advantage is that the prospects and customers can be included in the marketing mix of the business at any time of the day and any place in the world. Different products can be purchased online including clothing products. There are different methods of payment in online marketing. According to Mukherjee and Roy (2017), instead of different types of traditional payment methods like cheques or cash, in e-commerce, e-payment can be adopted such as use of credit/debit cards, prepaid cards, and mobile wallets. Developed nations have adopted such e-payment approaches, but in developing countries like Nigeria, a substantial proportion of e-customers are using cash on delivery (COD) (Adeyeye, 2014). Cash on delivery implies that the customer pays for the goods at the point of delivery (Halaweh, 2018). However, some online vendors insist on payment before delivery of goods.

Delivering also known as shipping is a link in the supply chain that directly affects the consumer and triggers their satisfaction. Delivery of goods entails the general process of supplying the products such that consumers get the exact products ordered online (Nwokah & Nwokah, 2016). The customer expects from the retailer to deliver the promised product in a trustworthy and appropriate manner (Seyed, Farzana, Ahasanul & Ali, 2011). Delivering goods to customers in e-marketing is a service that could influence the customers' satisfaction. Khalid, Lee, Choi and Ahn (2018) noted that customers' satisfaction is the assessment made by customers about a product or service, as to whether it has met with their expectations or needs. Consumer satisfaction is the result of comparing the expectations and the experience; in other words, the consumer is pleased when the delivery meets or exceeds their expectations. It is based on this background that the study was carried out to determine customers' satisfaction of delivery methods adopted in e-marketing of clothing products.

1.1. Statement of Problem

E-marketing in Nigeria has phenomenally fostered in recent years as a result of post COVID-19, cyberspace expansion and launching of various national and international e-vendors. However, the transition from traditional method of shopping to e-marketing created a sense of concern among

customers with respect to online fraud, inconsistency between the ordered product quality and the desired quality, unsuccessful shipping and delay in delivery of ordered products. Today, these concerns are at a much lower level, as people recognized the advantages offered by e-marketing. Devaraj, Fan and Kohli (2002) noted that due to technological innovation, the traditional mode of purchase has become inadequate for some individuals. People now prefer simpler modes for acquiring brands and reaching stores, and it can be stated that the internet has fundamentally changed the consumers' ideas on convenience, speed, price, product and service information. The biggest challenge for online shopping is to provide and maintain customer satisfaction. There is dearth of information on e-marketing of clothing products and customers' satisfaction of delivery methods which is the focus of the present study.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine e-marketing of clothing products and customers' satisfaction of delivery methods in Epe Local Government Area of Lagos State. Specifically, the study:

- (a) Determined the clothing products household members commonly purchased through e-marketing.
- (b) Ascertained the delivery methods adopted by vendors in e-marketing.
- (c) Determined customers satisfaction of delivery methods adopted in e-marketing.
- (d) Sought the problems customers face in delivery of clothing products in e-marketing.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) What are the clothing products household members commonly purchased through e-marketing?
- (b) What are the delivery methods adopted by vendors in e-marketing?
- (c) What are the determinants of customers' satisfaction of delivery methods adopted in e-marketing?
- (d) What are the problems customers face in delivery of clothing products in e-marketing?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design of the Study

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. According to Uzoagulu (2011), in descriptive survey research design, data are usually collected, organised, analysed and then described as they exist without interfering with them. In this study, the researchers sought the opinion of the household members through the use of questionnaire and thereafter, the data obtained were analysed and interpreted.

2.1.1. Ethics and Approval of Research

Approval was sought from the Local Government Area Council before distribution of the questionnaire to the respondents.

2.2. Area of the Study

The area of the study was Epe Local Government area in Lagos State. Epe is an urban area located on the north side of the Lekki Lagoon in Lagos State. Epe was chosen as area for the study because it is an urban area and there are several tertiary institutions in the area. Also, Epe was chosen because of the proximity to the researchers.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population for the study was 181,715 which consisted of household members in Epe (Source:

National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). Sample size for the study was 384. Sample size was determined using a standard statistical determinant table by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Two sampling techniques were adopted for the study. They included multi staged sampling technique and convenient sampling technique. In the first stage of the multi stage sampling technique, Lagos State was divided into three senatorial districts which included Lagos Central, Lagos East and Lagos West from which Lagos East was selected. In the second phase of the multi stage sampling technique, Lagos East senatorial district was divided into five local government areas that make up the district from which Epe was chosen. In the third phase of the multi stage sampling technique, Epe was divided into four districts / wards which included Agbowo, Ejinrin, Epe Town and Erodo. Ninety-six (94) households from each of these four districts / wards were used for the study. Convenient sampling technique was used to pick 96 household members from each of the four districts in Epe.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

Researchers' developed questionnaire was utilized for data collection. The questionnaire was titled "Questionnaire on E-Marketing Delivery of Products and Customer Satisfaction" (EDPCS). It consisted of two sections. (Section A and B). Section A elicited information on demographic characteristics of the respondents while section B was based on the purposes of the study. A four-point scale rated as follows were used: Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed, and Strongly Disagreed. The questionnaire was validated by three experts from the Department of Vocational Education, Yaba College of Technology, Epe Campus, Lagos State. Reliability of the instrument was determined through test-retest method and a reliability co-efficient of 0.97 was obtained using spearman's rank correlation method. This was considered appropriate as reliability index.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

Copies of the questionnaires were administered to the respondents and retrieved on the spot by the researchers.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Data was analysed using mean and standard deviation. For the decision rule, mean rating from 2.5 and above were considered agreed upon while mean rating of 2.49 and below were considered as disagreed upon.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* What are the clothing products household members commonly purchased through e-marketing?

Table 1: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation Responses of Clothing Products Commonly Purchased through E-marketing

S/N	Clothing Products Commonly Purchased through E-marketing	Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Decision
1	Dresses such as gowns	3.93	0.75	Agreed
2	Shoes	3.77	0.51	Agreed
3	Shirts	3.55	0.62	Agreed
4	Belts	3.71	0.58	Agreed
5	Bags	3.81	0.45	Agreed
6	Cap	3.70	0.82	Agreed
7	Sunglasses	3.57	0.49	Agreed
8	Wigs	3.98	0.42	Agreed

9	Bedding such as duvet and bed sheets	3.49	0.55	Agreed
10	Curtains	2.99	0.62	Agreed
11	Jewelries such as bangles, necklaces and ear rings	3.74	0.70	Agreed

Analysis in Table 1 indicated that all the highlighted items were agreed upon as clothing products commonly purchased through e-marketing. The mean responses ranged from 2.99 to 3.98 which was above the cutoff point of 2.50. Also, standard deviation ranged from 0.42 to 0.82 implying that the mean responses were not far from each other.

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3.2. *Research question two:* What are the delivery methods adopted by vendors in e-marketing?

Table 2: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation Responses of the Delivery Methods Adopted by Vendors in E-marketing

S/N	Delivery Methods Adopted by Vendors in E-marketing	Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Decision
1	Free delivery by e-marketing vendors	3.74	0.52	Agreed
2	Use of Courier services	3.59	0.68	Agreed
3	Delivery by sales representatives	3.85	0.78	Agreed
4	Picking up by customers	3.76	0.83	Agreed
5	Assigning pick up places in designated malls, supermarkets and warehouses	3.53	0.82	Agreed

Table 2 showed that all the highlighted items on delivery methods adopted by vendors in e-marketing were all accepted. All the responses had mean values ranging from 3.53 to 3.85 which is above the cutoff point of 2.50. The standard deviation responses ranged from 0.52 to 0.83 implying that the mean responses were not far from each other.

3.3. *Research question three:* What are the determinants of customers' satisfaction of delivery methods adopted in e-marketing?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Responses on Level of Customers Satisfaction of Delivery Methods adopted in E-marketing

S/N	Determinants of Customers Satisfaction of Delivery Methods adopted in E-marketing	Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Decision
<i>Customers are satisfied when:</i>				
1	Goods ordered are delivered well packaged without dents	3.98	0.29	Agreed
2	Goods ordered are delivered on agreed time without delay	3.77	0.41	Agreed
3	Products delivered are same quality with products ordered	3.95	0.21	Agreed
4	Products are delivered in good condition	3.97	0.52	Agreed
5	Products are delivered conveniently to ones location	3.90	0.71	Agreed

Analysis in Table 3 indicated that all the highlighted items were agreed upon as determinants of

customers' satisfactions of delivery methods adopted in e-marketing. The mean responses ranged from 3.77 to 3.98 which were above the cutoff point of 2.50. On the other hand, standard deviation ranged from 0.21 to 0.71 indicating that the mean responses were not far from each other.

3.4. *Research question four:* What are the problems customers face in delivery of clothing products in e-marketing?

Table 4: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation Responses of the Problems Customers Face in Delivery of Clothing Products in E-marketing

S/N	Problems Customers face in Delivery of Clothing Products in E-marketing	Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Decision
1	When products delivered are not same quality with products ordered	3.91	0.53	Agreed
2	When e-marketing vendors waste time in delivering products that are ordered	3.71	0.42	Agreed
3	Fear of online theft or hacking of accounts by e-marketing vendors	3.89	0.74	Agreed
4	Doubts on product quality	3.97	0.54	Agreed
5	Goods bought online are more expensive	3.77	0.47	Agreed
6	High cost of shipping and delivery services	3.59	0.48	Agreed

Analysis in Table 4 indicated that the highlighted items were agreed upon as problems customers face in delivery services adopted in e-marketing. The mean responses ranged from 3.59 to 3.97 which were above the cutoff point of 2.50. On the other hand, standard deviation ranged from 0.42 to 0.74 indicating that the mean responses were not far from each other.

The study revealed the clothing products commonly purchased through e-marketing by households in Epe, Lagos State. From the findings, clothing products commonly purchased through e-marketing included dresses such as gowns, shoes, shirts, belts, shoes, bags, caps, sunglasses, wigs and jewellerys such as bangles, necklaces and ear rings. In line with these findings, Sunitha and Gnanadhas (2014) noted that different products and services can be obtained online. The findings implies that households in Epe engage in online purchase of clothing products which can be attributed to large number of students in the four Tertiary Institutions in Epe as well as the industrial nature of the community.

The study showed that the delivery methods adopted by vendors in e-marketing included free delivery by e-marketing vendors, use of courier services, delivery by sales representatives, picking up by customers and assigning pick up places to designated malls and supermarkets. In further support of the finding, Park and Kim (2006) reported that the various delivery strategy adopted by online marketers included free delivery by companies, courier services, delivery by sales agent. Also in line with the findings, Nwokah and Nwokah (2016) stated that Nigeria has experienced an unprecedented increase in online shopping following the commencement of emergence of some online retailers who have dispatch riders that deliver goods and products to the customers.

This study indicated that the customers are satisfied with e-marketing vendors when goods ordered are delivered well packed without dents on products, goods ordered are delivered on agreed time without delay, products delivered are same quality with products ordered, products are delivered

in good condition and when products are delivered conveniently to one's location. In line with these findings, Pencarelli, Škerháková, Taha & Valentiny (2018) stated that product and service quality are indicators of online customers satisfaction and shopping experiences. Also in line with the findings, Mittal (2013) elaborated that the perception of service quality and excellent service delivery, influences the purchase behaviour of customers.

The current also indicated that the problems customers face in delivery methods adopted in e-marketing included products delivered not being same quality with products ordered, e-marketing vendors waste time in delivery of products ordered, fear of online theft or hacking of accounts by e-marketing vendors, doubts on product quality, goods bought online are more expensive and high cost of shipping and delivery services. In agreement with the findings, Pham, and Ahammad (2017) noted that the quality of a product cannot be known until the consumer examines it with his hands, which does not present difficulties in traditional retailers. However, this result to goods ordered for being different from goods supplied. According to Kitapci, Akdogan and Dortyol (2014), the common problems in online delivery of products ranges from delayed or late delivery of products, lost products, no one at home to sign and pick the products and products delivered being different from products ordered. In further support of the findings, Jung and Seock (2007) reported that frequent problems in delivery of products in online marketing included the parcel being left in an unsecure location (even if the parcel is not damaged, it has clearly been put at risk) or problems with late, missing or lost parcels.

The implication of the study to online vendors is on the need to ensure effective customer satisfaction in delivery of products. This also implies that the online vendors would adopt various delivery methods in ensuring that goods and services are appropriately delivered. The customers will get information about different delivery services available for e-marketing and how each of these can be harnessed in order to enhance the satisfaction they derive from e-marketing. The study was limited by time and difficulty in getting customers to fill the questionnaire. There was time constraints in going round the districts / wards used for the study. Hence, the use of convenience sampling technique where household members in the district/wards were reached by the researchers was used for the study. The suggestion for further study include an investigation on strategies for promoting online service delivery in Lagos state, students choice and preference of delivery of products in e-marketing and ways of promoting customer satisfaction in e-marketing.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that various clothing products can be purchased online. These clothing products include dresses, shoes bags, jewelries, wigs, belts and wrist watches. The delivery methods adopted by vendors in e-marketing included free delivery, use of courier services, delivery by sales representatives, picking up by customers and assigning pick up places to designated malls and supermarkets. Customers' satisfactions of delivery services adopted in e-marketing can be achieved when goods ordered are delivered well packaged without dents on products and when products delivered are same quality with products ordered. Problems customers face in delivery methods adopted in e-marketing included: when products delivered are not same quality with products ordered and when e-marketing vendors waste time in delivering products ordered. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that customers can compare prices of clothing products online while engaging in e- purchase. The right delivery method should

be adopted to ensure customer satisfaction. E-marketing vendors should ensure that clothing products ordered are same with products delivered.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

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Methodology: NOA, RAO, ORD, IN, JSS

Writing – original draft, review & editing: NOA, RAO, ORD, IN, JSS

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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